

Teaching Evaluation Questionnaire

Module Name CQC Final year research project

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	<i>Satisfied</i>	<i>Slightly</i>	<i>Not satisfied</i>
During the module/unit the lecturer:			
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2 Whether you are satisfied with the students' oral Presentation.	☒	☐	☐
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4 Whether you are satisfied with the students' research paper.	☐	☐	☒
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